

Long range scanning wind lidar
beyond 25 km range:

Current status and future perspectives

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2. WindRamp I Demonstrator
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Abacus Laser Activities

Litra S/XS (short to medium range wind)

Airborne wind lidar

Products of Abacus Laser

Green Wind Lidar

Litra L/XL (long-range wind)

Specialised Laser Sources

Scaling to >25 km: Research Project WindRamp

Supported by:

- 2020 – 2023
- Goal: Wind-Lidar with very long range (>25 km)
→ Half-hour forecasts for offshore wind parks

on the basis of a decision
by the German Bundestag

Test-Measurements from the lab

Test-Measurements from the lab

Initial horizontal measurements

~0.6° Elevation, 640 ns pulses, 4 kHz Pulse rate, 2 s average

Initial horizontal measurements

*~0.6° Elevation, 640 ns pulses, **3.5 kHz** Pulse rate, 2 s average*

Measurements at the Elbe river

Measurements at the Elbe river

METEK outside,
Abacus Inside...

Lineal

Linie Pfad Polygon Kreis 3D-Pfad 3D-Polygon

Strecke zwischen zwei Punkten am Boden messen

Kartenlänge: 30.001,20 Meter

Länge am Boden: 30.001,20

Richtung: 305,27 Grad

Mausnavigation

Lineal

Linie Pfad Polygon Kreis 3D-Pfad 3D-Polygon

Strecke zwischen zwei Punkten am Boden messen

Kartenlänge:	30.063,07	Meter
Länge am Boden:	30.062,90	
Richtung:	205,23	Grad

Mausnavigation

Measurements at the Elbe river

Plots by
Janna
Seifert,
ForWIND
Uni
Oldenburg

New Project WindRamp II

Supported by:

Federal Ministry
for Economic Affairs
and Climate Action

on the basis of a decision
by the German Bundestag

2024 – 2027

Goal: Demonstrate improved half hour forecast with novel lidar technology

→ New long-range prototype will be placed in offshore wind park

New horizontal measurements

Improved Scanner

- New prototype for offshore deployment
- Higher scanning precision
- Direction sensing
- Better control
- Improved climatization and environmental control

Next steps in WindRamp II

- Onshore test phase
- Offshore deployment and tests
- Research into impact on forecast

Future Perspectives

- Lidar Module: New laser technology
 - Range goal >40 km
 - Faster measurements
- Scanner: Further improved scanning control and sensing
- Applications:
 - Further research on forecast improvement
 - Offshore site evaluation
 - ? → Suggestions welcome...

Thank you for your attention

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